

ISic4407

Fragment of a land-lease contract

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

legal text

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Emiliano Arena

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Emiliano Arena,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

A chance find during construction works immediately to the south of the Church of S.Maria delle Balate in January 2013

Coordinates

37.996408, 14.261675

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza di Messina, inventory ME30908

Physical Description

Fragment of a large slab or stele, broken on all sides (possibly to create a block for building purposes after antiquity), with some traces of mortar on the reverse

Dimensions

Height 31 cm

Width 14 cm

Depth 10.2-11.3 cm

Layout

traces of two columns of Greek letters, with a space of 1-3 cm between. Traces of 12 lines of each column are preserved although not symmetrically

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-16: 8 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: 6 mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of Arena 2020

On the stone, Arena reads a small circle inside the Δ , and notes that the IE are joined at the top by a horizontal stroke

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Arena, Emiliano 2020. Epigrafe tardo-ellenistica inedita da Halaesa Archonidea: un nuovo esempio di 'locazione' fondiaria dall'Occidente greco. *Historika*. 9: 233-296.

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4407. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381916>

Photo E. Arena, courtesy Messina Soprintendenza BBCCAA